

Supporting parents through ECEC services: impact evaluation of a parenting support model in an area of disadvantage

Catarina Leitão & Nóirín Hayes

To cite this article: Catarina Leitão & Nóirín Hayes (05 May 2025): Supporting parents through ECEC services: impact evaluation of a parenting support model in an area of disadvantage, Early Years, DOI: [10.1080/09575146.2025.2498716](https://doi.org/10.1080/09575146.2025.2498716)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09575146.2025.2498716>

© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group.

[View supplementary material](#)

Published online: 05 May 2025.

[Submit your article to this journal](#)

[View related articles](#)

[View Crossmark data](#)

Supporting parents through ECEC services: impact evaluation of a parenting support model in an area of disadvantage

Catarina Leitão ^b

^aChildhood Development Initiative, Dublin, Ireland; ^bSchool of Education, Trinity College Dublin, Dublin, Ireland

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to evaluate the impact of a parenting support model, Powerful Parenting, on parents' partnership with early years educators, the home learning environment, and parental stress. The unique feature of this model involved locating a Parent/Carer Facilitator within each specific early childhood education and care setting to support parents. It has been implemented in an economically disadvantaged area in Ireland. A total of 44 parents in the intervention group and 35 in the comparison group completed questionnaires at two timepoints. No statistically significant differences were found between the groups. Implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic, the model may not have been delivered with the optimal approach to produce changes in the measured outcomes between the two assessments. However, the intervention group parents reported high satisfaction with the model. Further research into Powerful Parenting under more normal circumstances, in a post-pandemic context, will contribute to informing future parenting supports.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 15 November 2023
Accepted 21 April 2025

KEYWORDS

Parenting support; families; intervention; impact evaluation; early childhood

Introduction

Quality Early Childhood Education and Care (ECEC) responding to the needs of children and families has the potential to drive sustainable development through its multiplier effect on children and society (Bruckauf and Hayes 2017). ECEC services that include parenting support can improve the awareness of parents (herein referring to primary caregivers) about early development and their role in supporting it and children's developmental outcomes (Koshyk et al. 2020; Sheridan et al. 2011; Turner et al. 2017; Yoshikawa 1994). Parenting support can present indirectly as information or directly as services and can strengthen parents' knowledge, confidence, and skills to help achieve the best outcomes for children and their families (DCYA 2018).

In line with Bronfenbrenner's bio-ecological theory of human development, multiple levels of the surrounding environment affect a person's development (e.g. Bronfenbrenner

CONTACT Catarina Leitão Childhood Development Initiative, St Mark's Youth and Family Centre, Cookstown Lane, Fettercairn Tallaght, Dublin D24 PK6P, Ireland

 Supplemental data for this article can be accessed online at <https://doi.org/10.1080/09575146.2025.2498716>

© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group.

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. The terms on which this article has been published allow the posting of the Accepted Manuscript in a repository by the author(s) or with their consent.

and Morris 2006). Combining parenting support with ECEC services can strengthen home-school interactions (the home-school mesosystem) and promote children's learning (Gerber, Sharry, and Streek 2016; Sheridan et al. 2019). Also, ECEC services can potentially increase access to parenting support, an identified need in diverse countries, including Ireland, which was the context of the current study (OECD 2021; DCEDIY 2022). Ethnographic research in Ireland reinforced the conceptualisation of early years settings as 'communities of care' that can offer families a sense of belonging and support (Garrity and Canavan 2017).

A parenting support model within ECEC services

Powerful Parenting is a parenting support model that places one dedicated Parent/Carer Facilitator (PCF) within each ECEC service. The purpose of the PCF role is to support parents in engaging in children's learning and addressing families'/parents' needs, aiming to enhance partnerships with the ECEC service, the Home Learning Environment (HLE), and limit parental stress (stressors related to parenting). The model aims to promote positive interactions between children and their environments, such as the ECEC service and the home. Following Bronfenbrenner's theory (e.g. Bronfenbrenner and Morris 2006), the PCF acts as the conduit in strengthening home-school interactions, which have been considered foundational to interventions intending to increase family – school engagement (Smith et al. 2022).

Figure 1 shows the theory of change for the Powerful Parenting evaluation.

The support is offered to all parents accessing the ECEC services. The type, delivery mode and intensity of support activities vary based on parents'/families' needs, identified through conversations between PCFs and parents (e.g. during morning drop-off or group sessions). In addition, the ECEC practitioners can also link PCFs to follow up with parents to complement the work conducted with children (e.g. by sharing resources on learning), thus strengthening the connections between home and setting. The implemented activities can vary across the ECEC services. For this reason, Powerful Parenting is considered a locally responsive and flexible model in contrast to a standardised, curriculum-based programme.

PCFs offer support to parents through different modalities, including one-to-one and group work, at the ECEC service or families' home, and with parents and children together or parents only. PCFs can offer informational support, such as sharing resources about promoting children's learning/development. They can also, as required, deliver the Parents Plus Early Years Programme (e.g. Sharry, Hampson, and Fanning 2003),¹ an evidence-based programme aiming to support parents in fostering positive interactions with their children (during six to 12 weeks). Additionally, PCFs can provide practical support to parents accessing other services for children and families (e.g. contacting services and helping parents during applications). The support can include capacity building and coordination among PCFs and the ECEC service staff (e.g. to develop activities for children and parents).

Powerful Parenting has been coordinated by a non-governmental organisation in consultation with the ECEC services providing it and has received state funding. This organisation has held monthly community of practice meetings with the PCFs, where they can share and plan their work, and receive training. Staff taking on the PCF role must have

Figure 1. Theory of change for the powerful parenting evaluation.

a university degree in Early Childhood Education, Social Care, Social Work, Psychology, or equivalent, and they work up to 25 h per week.

Powerful Parenting includes elements that have been considered effective in parenting support, namely: a focus on more than one area of need; being easily accessible (located within specific ECEC settings); continuity between universal and targeted provision, tailored supports to adapt to families’ needs; coordination with other services (Anders et al. 2019; Cadima et al. 2017; Geraghty 2021; Molinuevo 2013; Moran et al. 2004); and offering more than one modality of delivery, including centre- and home-based (Blok et al. 2005; Britto et al. 2015; Engle et al. 2011).

The model aims to enhance the relationship between ECEC services and parents and the HLE [i.e. activities associated with children’s learning, such as playing with words and numbers, telling stories and singing, among others (Melhuish 2010)]. Outcomes related to parenting programmes within specific ECEC settings in Ireland (e.g. Parents Plus, which can be delivered by PCFs) included improved HLE and reduced parental stress (Gerber, Sharry, and Streek 2016; Hayes et al. 2013). Parents who received support in their parenting role or to work/study were found to be more likely to be involved in school activities, feel empowered to talk to their child’s early years educator and help their child learn at home (Corter et al. 2006; Reid, Webster-Stratton, and Beauchaine 2001). A positive association was found between ECEC providers’ practices to engage parents in their children’s development and education (e.g. sharing information on the child) and improved HLE activities, particularly in low-income families (Barnett et al. 2020).

Powerful Parenting seeks to reduce parental stress by supporting parents in addressing their needs, such as access to financial/material resources and support services, both for children and parents, as required. Parental stress can be amplified by challenging situations, such as poverty (Louie, Cromer, and Berry 2017), and providing support to parents can either directly reduce it (e.g. through practical assistance) or buffer the parents from being impacted by stress (Nixon, Swords, and Murray 2013; Parkes, Sweeting, and Wight 2015).

The development of Powerful Parenting was informed by findings from a previously implemented early years broad support system evaluated via a cluster randomised control trial over 2 years (Hayes et al. 2013). Setting-based features of the support system included an embryonic PCF component, a Parents Plus Community Course and setting components, such as the service organisation, the curriculum model, practitioners' qualifications and access to health supports, including speech and language therapy.

The current study

Powerful Parenting can be considered an innovative approach to parenting support in that it locates specific responsibilities and skills to a defined new role of PCF, one that is embedded within the ECEC setting, to specifically support parents and strengthen their engagement with the ECEC services. PCFs can leverage the potential of ECEC services as connecting hubs to link parents and children to information and additional supports. Given the responsibilities and skills to support parents, this role can contribute to supporting the early years educators, highlighted as a priority in Irish policy (DCEDIY 2021). Without support, educators may face barriers to potentiating parental involvement, which can be related to responsibilities, increased expectations and demands (Garrity and Canavan 2017; Oke et al. 2019).

Published research on parenting support during early childhood implemented in Europe, including Ireland, often describes interventions which are either centre- or home-based (rather than combined), manualised with set topics/number of sessions and delivered through community, social and/or health services, rather than directly from within the ECEC system itself (Bernedo et al. 2024; Cadima et al. 2017; Leitão 2023). Examples of interventions implemented for parents accessing ECEC services in Europe and Ireland encompass the Incredible Years Parenting Program (Webster-Stratton 2001),² Peep the Learning Together Programme,³ Triple P Positive Parenting Programme (Sanders 2012),⁴ and Parents Plus Early Years Programme (which can be delivered as a standalone intervention, although also included within Powerful Parenting). These interventions generally include a set of sessions offered by trained/accredited staff, not requiring an ongoing professional role within settings and available to support parents, such as the PCF. In the published research, there seems to be less emphasis on 'real-time' tailored parenting support over more extended periods (Dolan, Zegarac, and Arsic 2020; Osman et al. 2019).

ECEC provision, child/family health services and parenting/family support, including by Family Support Workers, can be integrated into comprehensive approaches, such as the UK Sure Start initiative,⁵ partially modelled on the US Head Start programme.⁶ These services have been organised in Sure Start Local Programmes/Children's Centres, in disadvantaged areas. In contrast, Powerful Parenting has been specifically located in individual community-based ECEC services. The PCF is an accredited ECEC staff member

employed to implement Powerful Parenting (not a key worker or external visitor), with the singular role of supporting parents and their linkage to the ECEC service.

The objective of this study was to analyse the Powerful Parenting's impact on parents' partnership with early years educators, frequency of HLE activities, and parental stress. Despite Powerful Parenting being informed by a previously researched parent support system which included an embryonic PCF component, this study is the first to evaluate the current version of the model including a comparison group. Data were collected at two time points: Time 1 (T1) and Time 2 (T2).

This study occurred during an academic year in which Powerful Parenting was being implemented in eight ECEC services in Ireland in a Dublin area identified as economically disadvantaged (Haase and Pratschke 2017). During this year, some ECEC services with the model needed to close for some weeks due to mandated COVID-19-related closures. Many support activities had to be delivered remotely (online/telephone) and outdoors, whereas before, these were conducted in person at the ECEC service and families' homes. The activities implemented across the services included one-to-one support and group activities for parents, and for children and parents (Table ST1 - Supplemental Material – shows examples of activities implemented during the year). In some services, PCFs delivered Parents Plus sessions online rather than within the ECEC settings and conducted home visits to deliver resources (e.g. materials for activities with children or food packs). PCFs supported parents in accessing services related to diverse needs, such as: financial support (e.g. social welfare, childcare costs); assessment of the child's health needs; access and inclusion supports focused on children's needs; child protection; speech and language development; and early intervention to support children with unmet additional or complex needs (Table ST2 shows the number of referrals reported).

Methodology

Context

A total of 213 children between 3- and 6-year-old attended the eight ECEC services with Powerful Parenting (on average, 27 children per service, from 10 to 68). The child-to-staff ratio ranged between four and eight children to one staff member. The eight PCFs delivering Powerful Parenting had an average of almost 6 years of experience in this role ($M = 5.65$; $SD = 7.19$; $Min = 0.75$, $Max = 21.17$). The seven managers of the ECEC services with the model had an average of almost 17 years of experience ($M = 16.50$; $SD = 3.21$; $Min = 13$, $Max = 20$; one manager coordinated two services).

Participants

Parents for the Intervention Group were recruited from the eight ECEC services implementing Powerful Parenting. Parents for the Comparison Group were recruited from ECEC services not implementing it, selected using purposive sampling: these services were located in areas characterized by a level of overall affluence/deprivation similar to those of the Intervention services (following the Pobal HP Deprivation Index; Haase and Pratschke 2017). Thirty-five ECEC services were informed about the study and asked to support the recruitment of participants.

ECEC services were not randomly assigned to the Intervention and Comparison Groups since Powerful Parenting was already being implemented in previous years, and its implementation needed to continue in the same services. Powerful Parenting is provided at ECEC service level. All interested parents/main caregivers with children attending the eight ECEC services with Powerful Parenting could be part of the Intervention Group. Before the start of the academic year, based on the number of children enrolled in these ECEC services in previous years, and the feedback of the organisation coordinating the model, the estimated target number was that at least 50% of parents – around 120 – would participate and be part of the Intervention Group. The estimated target number for the Comparison Group was also 120 participants so that both groups could have an approximate size. The inclusion criterion to become a participant was to be a parent/main caregiver of a child attending an ECEC service.

The final sample (participating in T1 and T2) had 79 participants: 44 in the Intervention Group and 35 in the Comparison Group. In terms of comparing the 44 parents of the Intervention Group with the whole group of parents attending the ECEC services with Powerful Parenting, the only information available was that they were living in the same Dublin area, characterised by economic disadvantage (no further details about the whole group were available). No participants were found to change between Intervention and

Table 1. Characteristics at T1 by group.

Variables	Intervention group		Comparison group		<i>g/d_{Cox}</i>
	<i>n</i>	<i>M(SD)/%</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>M(SD)/%</i>	
Child^a					
Age	44	3.87(0.69)	35	3.87(0.79)	0.001
Female	44	56.8%	35	45.7%	0.286
Not the first year in ECEC	44	63.6%	35	65.7%	-0.055
Not the parent's first child	42	54.8%	35	34.3%	0.506
Parent					
Age	41	33.17(4.51)	32	35.94(4.59)	-0.603
Female	44	90.9%	35	97.1%	-0.726
Kinship-Mother	44	93.2%	35	97.1%	-0.536
Language-English	44	93.2%	35	82.9%	0.624
Country of origin-Ireland	44	86.4%	35	65.7%	0.720
Ethnicity-White Irish	44	88.6%	35	65.7%	0.841
Education level-Tertiary	43	25.6%	35	62.9%	-0.957
Employment status-In paid employment	44	52.3%	35	77.1%	-0.673
Marital status-Married/Civil partnership	43	39.5%	35	71.4%	-0.805
Household					
Type of household-Two parents living together	43	72.1%	34	88.2%	-0.637
No. children in household	44	2.02(0.95)	35	1.89(0.83)	0.151
No. adults in household	44	2.02 (0.70)	35	1.97 (0.45)	0.084
No social welfare	42	57.1%	34	58.8%	-0.042
No medical card	42	54.8%	34	82.4%	-0.811
No support services	44	72.7%	35	85.7%	-0.487
Outcome measures					
Sharing information-T1	44	21.64(2.62)	33	21.45(2.80)	0.067
Seeking information-T1	44	13.59(1.54)	35	13.77(1.65)	-0.112
Adult relations-T1	44	22.05(5.14)	35	21.26(4.35)	0.162
HLE-T1	41	35.71(8.42)	35	35.91(8.02)	-0.025
Parental stress-T1	43	35.40(8.42)	32	36.88(7.41)	-0.183

The variables with percentages were dichotomous, with the category shown coded as 1 and the 'Other' category as 0. 'No support services' corresponded to none of the following: Child and Family Agency; HSE-Psychology, Speech and language therapy, Occupational Therapy; Assessment of Need; housing, adult disability, and/or addiction services.

Comparison ECEC services from T1 to T2. [Table 1](#) shows the participants' characteristics at T1 by group.

Following What Works Clearinghouse (2022), equivalence between the two groups at T1 was analysed by calculating Hedges' g and Cox index (d_{Cox}), as shown in [Table 1](#). Equivalence for outcome measures at T1 was considered satisfactory (given that these measures were included in the subsequent analysis of variance for repeated measures and $|g| \leq 0.25SD$).

Concerning demographics, equivalence was satisfied for child's age and social welfare receipt ($|g/d_{Cox}| \leq 0.05SD$) and year in the ECEC service, and the number of children and adults in the household with adjustment ($0.05SD < |g/d_{Cox}| \leq 0.25SD$). Equivalence was not found for the other demographics ($|g/d_{Cox}| > 0.25SD$). The Intervention Group had younger parents on average; a higher percentage of parents whose child attending the ECEC service was not their first, who were female and mothers (however, dichotomous outcomes can yield large d_{Cox} , especially for base rates close to 0% or 100%), born in Ireland, White Irish, speaking English at home, receiving support services and state medical card (indicative of lower income); a lower percentage of parents who completed tertiary education, and were in paid employment, married/in a civil partnership and living together with the other parent.

Procedures

The contacted ECEC services were asked to share information on the study with parents, including the link to the online questionnaire used. A parent/caregiver per family was invited to participate. The study description indicated the goal of recruiting participants with and without Powerful Parenting in their ECEC services. Therefore, participants were not blind regarding their assigned group. The two groups received different links to the questionnaire, increasing the certainty about each participant's group.

Completing the questionnaire was expected to take around 20 min and could take place at the participants' convenience. Participants were identified with a code at T1 to match their responses at T2 (name initials and a date). ECEC services were also asked to share information about T2. T1 occurred during December–January, and T2 during May–June of the same academic year.

Ethics

Ethics approval was obtained from the National Child and Family Agency's (Tusla) Research and Ethics Committee (reference: PEAR EC). Information on the study and a consent form were included at the start of the online questionnaire. Data were treated confidentially and anonymised.

Instruments

Participants' sociodemographic characteristics were collected via a questionnaire developed by the organisation coordinating Powerful Parenting, applied in previous evaluations. When answering about their child, participants were asked to consider the child

attending the ECEC service from which they received the invitation to participate in the study and the one born first if there was more than one child in this service.

Parents' partnerships-related behaviours toward early years educators were evaluated through the Caregiver–Parent Partnership Scale (Owen, Ware, and Barfoot 2000; Ware et al. 1995). The items are rated on a five-point Likert scale: higher scores indicate more frequent partnership-relevant behaviours. Items can be grouped into three categories: a) Sharing information about the child (five items, scores from 5 to 25); b) Seeking information about the child (three items, scores from 3 to 15); and c) Adult relations – supportive behaviour towards the educators (six items, scores from 6 to 30). In the current study, Cronbach's alphas at T1 and T2 were .73 and .78 for Sharing Information, .63 and .70 for Seeking Information, and .77 and .80 for Adult Relations.

The HLE was evaluated via the seven items on the Parent's Role in Fostering Home Learning used in the Growing Up in Ireland study (McCrory et al. 2013). The items ask about the frequency of the following activities with the child: reading to the child; helping to learn the alphabet/letters; numbers/counting, songs/poems/nursery rhymes; playing games (e.g. board games); painting/drawing/colouring/play-doh; and playing active games (e.g. football). The items are rated on an eight-point Likert scale. The total score can range from 0 to 49: higher scores indicate a higher frequency of HLE activities. Cronbach's alphas were .72 and .76 at T1 and T2.

Parental stress was evaluated using the Parental Stress Scale (Berry and Jones 1995). It includes 18 items asking how parents feel about their parenting role, rated on a five-point Likert scale. The total score range from 18 to 90: higher scores indicate higher parental stress levels. In line with national research (e.g. Centre for Effective Services 2019), a total score was calculated in the current study; Cronbach's alpha was .82 at T1 and T2. However, the original research (Berry and Jones 1995) suggested a 4-factor structure.

Satisfaction with Powerful Parenting and the relationship with the PCF was assessed within the Intervention Group at T2: six items were rated on a five-point Likert scale and analysed individually, and there was also the openended question 'How can we improve parental engagement in our service?'.

At T2, Comparison Group participants were asked whether they received professional help/advice on child health/wellbeing, childrearing or parenting, or participated in any parenting support programme/course in the last 6 months (response options: No; Yes, provided by the preschool; Yes, provided by other services [not the preschool]; I do not know).

Data analysis

An analysis of variance for repeated measures was conducted for each outcome. Time (T1 outcome, T2 outcome) was the within-subjects factor. Group (Intervention, Comparison) was the between-subjects factor. Imbalanced demographics that could be related to both the assigned group and assessed outcomes, such as those indicative of socioeconomic circumstances and household composition, were included as covariates. Given that parents in the Intervention Group could access Powerful Parenting before T1, two models were tested (following Elwert and Winship 2014; Kitamura 2024).

Model 1 controlled for imbalanced demographics not or unlikely to be affected by Powerful Parenting: child's gender, year in the ECEC service, being the parent's first child;

Table 2. Analysis of variance for repeated measures of the effect Time*Group.

Domain	Model 1					Model 2				
	IG n	CG n	F	Sig	η^2	IG n	CG n	F	Sig	η^2
Sharing information	39	30	.499	.483	.008	36	28	1.198	.279	.024
Seeking information	38	32	1.038	.312	.016	36	30	.617	.436	.012
Adult relations	38	30	.207	.651	.003	35	28	.313	.579	.006
HLE	37	31	.001	.969	.001	34	29	.000	.994	.000
Parental Stress	38	28	.411	.524	.007	35	27	.828	.368	.017

IG = Intervention Group; IC = Comparison Group. η^2 = Partial Eta Squared.

parent's age, ethnicity (associated with country and language which were not included as covariates; Cramér's V of .964 and .685, $p < .001$) and education level (although PCFs could provide support to parents to enrol in formal education, a change in the degree hold would be unlikely from T1/December to T2/June). Although demographics such as parent's gender and kinship could also potentially affect the measured outcomes, they were not included, given the very low percentage of males and caregivers other than mothers within each group.

For sensitivity analysis, Model 2 controlled for the previous covariates plus those potentially affected by Powerful Parenting: employment, marital status, type of household, number of children and adults in the household, medical card, and use of other support services (PCFs could provide support on accessing employment, financial/material resources, or services that could lead to changes in the household composition, e.g. child protection).

The responses 'Prefer not to say' and 'I don't know' were coded as missing data. Only cases with data on the variables were included.

The analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS 28.

Results

Table 2 shows the results of the analysis of variance for repeated measures for the interaction Time*Group (Tables ST3–7 in Supplemental Material show the models with all included covariates). No statistically significant differences were found between the Intervention and Comparison Groups regarding parents' partnership-related behaviours toward early years educators (Sharing information, Seeking information, and Adult relations), frequency of HLE activities, and Parental stress, in Model 1 and Model 2.

Regarding Satisfaction with Powerful Parenting and the relationship with the PCF within the Intervention Group at T2, all items – which were about the interaction with the PCF and the quality and variety of the supports – were rated positively by more than 77% of parents (Table ST8). Among the 30 parents replying to the question on suggestions for improvement, 24 indicated not having suggestions or that improvements were not needed, three suggested more communication about children's day/progress, and three more group activities.

Regarding the involvement with other parenting support interventions in the last 6 months within the Comparison Group at T2, most participants were not involved; 26% attended a parenting programme/course. Most of the interventions accessed were provided by services other than the ECEC service (Table ST9).

Discussion

Although Powerful Parenting includes elements recognised as effective in the literature to promote positive outcomes for families (e.g. Anders et al. 2019; Cadima et al. 2017), no statistically significant impacts were found regarding partnership-related behaviours toward early years educators, frequency of HLE activities, and parental stress.

Regarding partnership-related behaviours, the evaluation involved participants estimating the frequency of contact with early years educators. It is important to consider the possibility of parents with access to Powerful Parenting seeking and sharing information about specific topics with PCFs. In the same academic year, in an interview study with 27 parents from the ECEC services with the model on their satisfaction with the support provided, an identified theme referred to PCFs being perceived as a central point of contact (participants could be different from those in this study; Leitão 2022). Considering Powerful Parenting's aim of enhancing parents-ECEC services partnerships, future research could focus on indicators other than involving the frequency of contact with educators (e.g. such as feeling empowered to talk to the educator or the likelihood of being involved in service activities). Other components could also be explored within Powerful Parenting, in consultation with parents and the ECEC staff: for instance, interventions aiming to increase family – school engagement have included joint workshops with teachers and parents focused on relationship building (Smith et al. 2022).

Concerning the HLE, the frequency of home visits has been set according to the needs of each family (including before the pandemic). However, due to the pandemic, they mainly occurred to deliver resources during the academic year of this study instead of being opportunities to work with or provide further support to parents (as before the pandemic). This might have made it more difficult for PCFs to make recommendations based on observations of the HLE or to promote opportunities for parents to practice parenting skills, which has been associated with positive outcomes, including from parenting support interventions in ECEC (Britto et al. 2015; Grindal et al. 2016; Kaminski et al. 2008). Also, the evaluation of the previous version of the model (Hayes et al. 2013), which occurred over 2 years, indicated that the more sessions of the Parents Plus Community Course parents attended, the higher the HLE score. At the time of the current research, the implementation of Parents Plus was also subject to changes due to the pandemic (online instead of in person), and it was not possible to collect data on the attendance of each participating parent. Collecting information on the availability/time and opportunities for parents to promote HLE activities could also be relevant to characterise the Intervention and Comparison Groups.

Although parenting support's impact on parental and general stress can differ (Melson, Windecker-Nelson, and Schwarz 1998), parents in both groups could have experienced COVID-19-related stress that Powerful Parenting could not affect. Increased stress during the pandemic was an identified challenge by parents in the same intervention ECEC services (Leitão et al. 2022).

Within Powerful Parenting, providing tailored support to respond to parents'/families' specific needs was expected to reduce parental stress. Additionally, reduced parental stress was an outcome found in a study of Parents Plus in ECEC services (Gerber, Sharry, and Streek 2016), which is included in the model. Given that PCFs contacted parents remotely more often than before the pandemic,

it is possible that this affected the creation of trustful relationships, key to responding to families' needs effectively (Santos et al. 2024). The PCFs themselves may have been under stress, which may have impacted the quality of their engagement with parents.

Although Powerful Parenting seeks to meet each family's needs, it might not be sufficiently targeted. The model includes activities with diverse durations, frequencies and intensities, which may not have been delivered with the optimal dosage to produce changes in the measured outcomes (e.g. in parenting support in ECEC, home visits less than once a month were found to have lower effects than those with higher frequency on children's outcomes; Grindal et al. 2016). Despite the core responsibilities of the PCF role being somewhat standardised across the ECEC services, and some activities being planned with all PCFs together, Powerful Parenting requires flexibility to provide tailored support. Effective implementation of interventions can require monitoring both core components and agreed variations (Kemp 2016). In the future research, collecting data on the dosage of the activities received by parents and including it in the analyses could be relevant to clarify possible impacts.

Most of the Comparison Group's parents reported not receiving professional parenting support during the 6 months before T2. It would have been relevant to account for possible effects from other parenting supports in both Intervention and Comparison Groups and not, as was the case, only in the Comparison Group.

High levels of satisfaction with the model and relationship with the PCF were found among Intervention parents. Assessing the perceptions of both Intervention and Comparison Groups about the support received from their ECEC service would be relevant to exploring the impact of the PCFs' role. Both groups could be asked about the amount and type of support received, and their perceptions of feeling supported.

Limitations

Equivalence between the Intervention and Comparison Groups at T1 was not demonstrated for a number of demographics, hindering inferences about Powerful Parenting impacts. The initial plan was to include eight Comparison ECEC services that could be matched to Intervention ECEC services based on the setting capacity, staff-to-child ratio, and staff experience/qualifications. However, given that ECEC services were facing COVID-19-related measures, it was necessary to invite more services to facilitate the recruitment of parents for the Comparison Group. The scheduling of this study coincided with the arrival of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Changes in the methodology due to the pandemic led to delays in data collection. T1 and T2 assessments were only four to 6 months apart (depending on the date parents completed the questionnaire). Although we did not find research on similar models to estimate the duration of the intervention required to detect possible impacts, a more consistent impact has been found for parenting support interventions that last over 2 years (Britto et al. 2015; Brocklesby 2019).

The results obtained cannot be generalised to a larger population (the sample was not representative). Also, parents with positive experiences with the model or ECEC service could have been more willing to participate. Further studies would be required to explore whether the current findings generalise to other outcomes and contexts.

Due to the small sample size and concerns with statistical power, data were not nested within ECEC services, not accounting for possible effects related to the services' characteristics (e.g. practices for involving families can influence parent–educator relationships; Smith et al. 2022).

Concerning the small sample size, the questionnaire length may have taken longer to complete than recommended for online questionnaires (e.g. 10–15 min). Participants could decide not to complete it. Also, some responses could not be matched between T1 and T2 based on the codes created.

Self-report measures can be prone to social desirability. There can also be compensatory effects in the case of the Comparison Group. Observational measures can be relevant in evaluating intervention impacts, but these were not possible due to the pandemic. Collecting qualitative data from participants could also help interpret results (e.g. views on the quality of the support received and responsiveness to their needs).

Notes

1. www.parentsplus.ie.
2. www.incredibleyears.com.
3. www.peeple.org.uk.
4. www.triplep.net.
5. www.gov.uk/find-sure-start-childrens-centre.
6. headstart.gov.

Acknowledgments

We wish to acknowledge our gratitude to the participants in this study.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Funding

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement [No. 890925].

ORCID

Catarina Leitão <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-1879-9263>
Nóirín Hayes <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-8086-5474>

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8252669>, reference number 8,252,669.

References

- Anders, Y., J. Cadima, K. Ereky-Stevens, F. Cohen, M. Trauernicht, and J. Schünke. 2019. Integrative Report on Parent and Family-Focused Support to Increase Educational Equality. <https://www.isotis.org/en/publications/integrative-report-on-parent-and-family-focused-support-to-increase-educational-equality/>.
- Barnett, M. A., K. W. Paschall, A. M. Mastergeorge, C. A. Cutshaw, and S. M. Warren. 2020. "Influences of Parent Engagement in Early Childhood Education Centers and the Home on Kindergarten School Readiness." *Early Childhood Research Quarterly* 53:260–273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2020.05.005>.
- Benedo, I. M., A. Almeida, S. Byrne, L. González-Pasarín, N. Pečnik, O. Cruz, A. Uka, D. Skučienė, and L. Šumskaitė. 2024. "The Use of Evidence-Based Programmes in Family Support Across Europe: A Comparative Survey Study." *Children and Youth Services Review* 158:107455. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2024.107455>.
- Berry, J. O., and W. H. Jones. 1995. "The Parental Stress Scale: Initial Psychometric Evidence." *Journal of Social and Personal Relationships* 12 (3): 463–472. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0265407595123009>.
- Blok, H., R. G. Fukkink, E. C. Gebhardt, and P. P. M. Leseman. 2005. "The Relevance of Delivery Mode and Other Programme Characteristics for the Effectiveness of Early Childhood Intervention." *International Journal of Behavioral Development* 29 (1): 35–47. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01650250444000315>.
- Britto, P. R., L. A. Ponguta, C. Reyes, and R. Karnati. 2015. *A Systematic Review of Parenting Programmes for Young Children in Low and Middle Income Countries*, UNICEF. https://www.unicef.org/sites/default/files/press-releases/media-P_Shanker_final_Systematic_Review_of_Parenting_ECD_Dec_15_copy.pdf.
- Brocklesby, S. 2019. *A National Review of the Community Mothers Programme*. Vol. 1. Katharine Howard Foundation, The Community Foundation for Ireland. http://www.khf.ie/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/National-Review-of-the-Community-Mothers-Programme-Full-Report-FINAL-18-04_19.pdf.
- Bronfenbrenner, U., and P. A. Morris. 2006. "The Bioecological Model of Human Development." In *Handbook of Child Psychology: Theoretical Models of Human Development*, edited by W. Lerner and R. M. Damon, 793–828. 6th ed. Vol. 1. New York: Wiley.
- Bruckauf, Z., and N. Hayes. 2017. "Quality of Childcare and Pre-Primary Education: How Do We Measure It?" United Nations. <https://doi.org/10.18356/2BE8313E-EN>.
- Cadima, J., G. Nata, M. Evangelou, Y. Anders, and Parental Support ISOTIS Team. 2017. "Inventory and Analysis of Promising and Evidence-Based Parent- and Family- Focused Support Programs." <http://www.isotis.org/resources/publications/isotis-publications>.
- Centre for Effective Services. 2019. "Information Pack to Support the Assessment of Parenting Outcomes." <https://whatworks.gov.ie/resources/collecting-outcome-data-in-services/>.
- Corter, C., J. Bertrand, J. Pelletier, T. Griffin, D. K. McKay, S. Patel, P. Ioannone, et al. 2006. Toronto First Duty: Phase 1 Summary Report: Evidence-Based Understanding of Integrated Foundations for Early Childhood. http://www.toronto.ca/firstduty/TFD_Summary_Report_June06.pdf.
- DCEDIY. 2021. "Nurturing Skills: The Workforce Plan for Early Learning and Care and School-Age Childcare 2022-2028." <https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/97056-nurturing-skills-the-workforce-plan-for-early-learning-and-care-elc-and-school-age-childcaresac-2022-2028/>.
- DCEDIY. 2022. *Supporting Parents: A National Model of Parenting Support Services*. Dublin: DCEDIY. <http://www.gov.ie/supportingparents/>.
- DCYA. 2018. "First 5: A Whole-Of-Government Strategy for Babies, Young Children and Their Families." <https://assets.gov.ie/31184/62acc54f4bdf4405b74e53a4afb8e71b.pdf>.
- Dolan, P., N. Zegarac, and J. Arsic. 2020. "Family Support as a Right of the Child." *Social Work and Social Sciences Review* 21 (2): 8–26. <https://doi.org/10.1921/swssr.v21i2.1417>.
- Elwert, F., and C. Winship. 2014. "Endogenous Selection Bias: The Problem of Conditioning on a Collider Variable." *Annual Review of Sociology* 40 (1): 31–53. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-soc-071913-043455>.

- Engle, P. L., L. C. Fernald, H. Alderman, J. Behrman, C. O’Gara, A. Yousafzai, M. C. de Mello, et al. 2011. “Strategies for Reducing Inequalities and Improving Developmental Outcomes for Young Children in Low-Income and Middle-Income Countries.” *Lancet* 378 (9799): 1339–1353. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(11\)60889-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(11)60889-1).
- Garrity, S., and J. Canavan. 2017. “Trust, Responsiveness and Communities of Care: An Ethnographic Study of the Significance and Development of Parent-Caregiver Relationships in Irish Early Years Settings.” *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal* 25 (5): 747–767. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2017.1356546>.
- Geraghty, R. 2021. “Development of a National Model of Parenting Support Services – Literature Review.” Dublin. <https://www.gov.ie/ga/eolas-eagraiochta/eb017-developing-a-national-model-of-parenting-support-services/>.
- Gerber, S.-J., J. Sharry, and A. Streek. 2016. “Parent Training: Effectiveness of the Parents Plus Early Years Programme in Community Preschool Settings.” *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal* 24 (4): 602–614. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2016.1189726>.
- Grindal, T., J. Bonnes Bowne, H. Yoshikawa, H. S. Schindler, G. J. Duncan, K. Magnuson, and J. P. Shonkoff. 2016. “The Added Impact of Parenting Education in Early Childhood Education Programs: A Meta-Analysis.” *Children and Youth Services Review* 70:238–249. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2016.09.018>.
- Haase, T., and J. Pratschke. 2017. “The 2016 Pobal HP Deprivation Index for Small Areas: Dataset for Local Electoral Areas (2015 Lea)(excel).” <http://trutzhause.eu/deprivation-index/the-2016-pobal-hp-deprivation-index-for-small-areas/>.
- Hayes, N., I. Siraj-Blatchford, S. Keegan, and E. Goulding. 2013. “Evaluation of the Early Years Programme of the Childhood Development Initiative.” Dublin. https://www.cdi.ie/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/CDI-Early_Years_Report_24.01-web-1.pdf.
- Kaminski, J. W., L. Anne Valle, J. H. Filene, and C. L. Boyle. 2008. “A Meta-Analytic Review of Components Associated with Parent Training Program Effectiveness.” *Journal of Abnormal Child Psychology* 36 (4): 567–589. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10802-007-9201-9>.
- Kemp, L. 2016. “Adaptation and Fidelity: A Recipe Analogy for Achieving Both in Population Scale Implementation.” *Prevention Science* 17 (4): 429–438. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11121-016-0642-7>.
- Kitamura, K. 2024. “School-Based Early Childhood Education and Children’s Development in Urban Nepal.” *Early Education and Development* 35 (7): 1591–1613. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10409289.2023.2257574>.
- Koshyk, J., T. Wilson, A. Stewart-Tufescu, M. D’Souza, R. M. Chase, and J. Mignone. 2020. “The Ripple Effect: Examining the Impact on Parents of an Abecedarian Early Child Care Intervention in an Urban Social Housing Development.” *Journal of Early Childhood Research* 19 (1): 40–54. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1476718X20966696>.
- Leitão, C. 2022. *Evaluation of the CDI Parenting Support Model: Powerful Parenting*. Dublin: Childhood Development Initiative.
- Leitão, C. 2023. “Supporting Parents with Young Children in Ireland: Context, Policies and Research-Supported Interventions.” *Irish Studies Review*: 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09670882.2023.2265834>.
- Leitão, C., J. Shumba, M. Quinn, and G. Hutchinson. 2022. “Perspectives and Experiences of Covid-19: Two Irish Studies of Families in Disadvantaged Communities.” *PLOS ONE* 17 (7): 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0270472>.
- Louie, A., L. Cromer, and J. Berry. 2017. “Assessing Parenting Stress: Review of the Use and Interpretation of the Parental Stress Scale.” *The Family Journal* 25:359–367. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1066480717731347>.
- McCorry, C., J. Williams, A. Murray, A. Quail, and M. Thornton. 2013. “Growing Up in Ireland National Longitudinal Study of Children. Infant Cohort. Design, Instrumentation and Procedures for the Infant Cohort at Wave Two (3 Years).” <https://www.growingup.gov.ie/pubs/BKMNEXT253.pdf>.
- Melhuish, E. 2010. “Why Children, Parents and Home Learning are Important.” In *Early Childhood Matters: Evidence from the Effective Pre-School and Primary Education Project*, edited by K. Sylva, E. Melhuish, P. Sammons, I. Siraj-Blatchford, and B. Taggart, 44–70. London: Routledge.

- Melson, G. F., E. Windecker-Nelson, and R. Schwarz. 1998. "Support and Stress in Mothers and Fathers of Young Children." *Early Education and Development* 9 (3): 261–281. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15566935eed0903_4.
- Molinuevo, D. 2013. "Parenting Support in Europe." <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/publications/2013/parenting-support-europe>.
- Moran, P., D. Gbate, A. Van Der Merwe, and Policy Research Bureau. 2004. *What Works in Parenting Support? A Review of the International Evidence*. London: Department for Education and Skills.
- Nixon, E., L. Swords, and A. Murray. 2013. Parenting and Infant Development. Infant Cohort Report No. 3. Growing Up in Ireland: National Longitudinal Study of Children. Dublin. <https://www.growingup.ie/pubs/BKMNEXT244.pdf>.
- OECD. 2021. "Looking Beyond COVID-19: Strengthening Family Support Services Across the OECD. Employment, Labour and Social Affairs Policy Briefs." <https://www.oecd.org/els/family/fss2021-brief-covid.pdf>.
- Oke, M., K. Filipovic, J. Lambert, and N. Hayes. 2019. *Predictors of Burnout Amongst Early Childhood Educators*. Dublin: National Early Childhood Ireland Research Conference.
- Osman, F., R. Flacking, M. K. Allvin, and U. K. Schön. 2019. "Qualitative Study Showed That a Culturally Tailored Parenting Programme Improved the Confidence and Skills of Somali Immigrants." *Acta Paediatrica* 108 (8): 1482–1490. <https://doi.org/10.1111/APA.14788>.
- Owen, M. T., A. M. Ware, and B. Barfoot. 2000. "Caregiver-Mother Partnership Behavior and the Quality of Caregiver-Child and Mother-Child Interactions." *Early Childhood Research Quarterly* 15 (3): 413–428. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0885-2006\(00\)00073-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0885-2006(00)00073-9).
- Parke, A., H. Sweeting, and D. Wight. 2015. "Parenting Stress and Parent Support Among Mothers with High and Low Education." *Journal of Family Psychology* 29 (6): 907–918. <https://doi.org/10.1037/fam0000129>.
- Reid, M. J., C. Webster-Stratton, and T. P. Beauchaine. 2001. "Parent Training in Head Start: A Comparison of Program Response Among African American, Asian American, Caucasian, and Hispanic Mothers." *Prevention Science* 2 (4): 209–227. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1013618309070>.
- Sanders, M. R. 2012. "Development, Evaluation, and Multinational Dissemination of the Triple P-Positive Parenting Program." *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology* 8 (1): 345–379. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-clinpsy-032511-143104>.
- Santos, R. D., A. Burgund Isakov, C. Martins, A. Pereira Antunes, N. Zegarac, and C. Nunes. 2024. "Professional Skills in Family Support: A Systematic Review." *Social Sciences* 13 (3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci13030176>.
- Sharry, J., G. Hampson, and M. Fanning. 2003. "Parents Plus - 'The Early Years' Programme: A Video-Based Parenting Guide to Promoting Young Children's Development and to Preventing and Managing Behaviour Problems." <https://www.parentsplus.ie/>.
- Sheridan, S. M., L. L. Knoche, K. A. Kupzyk, C. Pope Edwards, and C. A. Marvin. 2011. "A Randomized Trial Examining the Effects of Parent Engagement on Early Language and Literacy: The Getting Ready Intervention." *Journal of School Psychology* 49 (3): 361–383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsp.2011.03.001>.
- Sheridan, S. M., T. E. Smith, S. N. B. Elizabeth Moorman Kim, S. Park, and S. Park. 2019. "A Meta-Analysis of Family-School Interventions and Children's Social-Emotional Functioning: Moderators and Components of Efficacy." *Review of Educational Research* 89 (2): 296–332. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/45277274>.
- Smith, T. E., S. R. Holmes, M. E. Romero, and S. M. Sheridan. 2022. "Evaluating the Effects of Family-School Engagement Interventions on Parent-Teacher Relationships: A Meta-Analysis." *School Mental Health* 14 (2): 278–293. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12310-022-09510-9>.
- Turner, K. M. T., C. K. Dittman, J. C. Rusby, and S. Lee. 2017. "Parenting Support in an Early Childhood Learning Context." In *The Power of Positive Parenting: Transforming the Lives of Children, Parents, and Communities Using the Triple P System*, edited by M. R. Sanders, T. G. Mazzucchelli, M. R. Sanders, and T. G. Mazzucchelli. New York: Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/med-psych/9780190629069.003.0021>.

- Ware, A. M., B. Barfoot, A. S. Rusher, and M. T. Owen. 1995. "The caregiver role in the parent-caregiver partnership: Its relationship to the child care environment." *Poster Session Presented at the Biennial Meeting of the Society for Research in Child Development*, Indianapolis, IN.
- Webster-Stratton, C. 2001. *The Parent and Child Series: A Comprehensive Course Divided into Four Programs – Leaders' Guide*. Seattle: The Incredible Years.
- What Works Clearinghouse. 2022. *What Works Clearinghouse Procedures and Standards Handbook, Version 5.0*. U.S. Department of Education, Institute of Education Sciences. https://ies.ed.gov/ncee/wwc/Docs/referenceresources/Final_WWC-HandbookVer5.0-0-508.pdf.
- Yoshikawa, H. 1994. "Prevention as Cumulative Protection: Effects of Early Family Support and Education on Chronic Delinquency and Its Risks." *Psychological Bulletin* 115 (1): 28–54. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.115.1.28>.